

Chromium(III), iron(III) and cobalt(II) complexes of 14- and 16-membered tetraazamacrocycles

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Abstract : 2+2 Cyclocondensation of 3,4-hexanedione with 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane in the presence of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} as templates has yielded complexes of the types [ML(NO₃)₂]₂NO₃ and [CoL(NO₃)₂] [where M = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and L = 2,3,9,10-tetraethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene or 2,3,10,11-tetraethyl-1,4,9,12-tetraazacyclohexadeca-1,3,9,11-tetraene]. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic measurements, FAB mass, IR and electronic spectra.

Keywords : Macrocylic complexes, transition metal complexes, IR spectra, FAB mass.

Due to resemblance of macrocyclic complexes with biologically active compounds, they are used in identification of diseased and normal tissues¹. Fe^{III} complexes of 1,4,7,10-tetrakis(carboxymethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane and 1,4,7-tris(carboxymethyl)-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane have been evaluated for use as potential contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)². In the present paper Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} complexes of 2,3,9,10-tetraethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene (L¹) and 2,3,10,11-tetraethyl-1,4,9,12-tetraazacyclohexadeca-1,3,9,11-tetraene (L²) are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} nitrates with 3,4-hexanedione and 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios result in the formation of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes (Scheme 1).

M	k	x	m	n
Cr	3	9	1	3, 4
Fe	3	9	1	3, 4
Co	2	6	0	3, 4

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are coloured solids and decompose on heating. All the complexes are insoluble in water, methanol, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene but are soluble in dimethylsulphoxide. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Infrared spectra : In the IR spectra of macrocyclic complexes strong absorption bands in the region 1600–1625 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to νC=N vibrations. In the IR spectra of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from dihydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridine, Saraswat and Rana³ have assigned absorption bands at 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ to νC=N. Bands observed at ~825 and ~1385 cm⁻¹ in all the Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles may be assigned to ionic nitrate. Curtis and Curtis⁴ have reported bands at 823 and 1368 cm⁻¹ due to out of plane deformation and doubly degenerate stretching vibrations respectively of ionic nitrate in [Ni(en)₃](NO₃)₂. The presence of coordinated unidentate nitrate in all the reported complexes has been confirmed by the appearance of absorption bands at 1450–1490, 1025–1050 and 742–786 cm⁻¹ (ν₄). In case of transition metal complexes of tetra-N-methylcyclam the absorption bands at 1460, 1280, 1029, 805 and 739 cm⁻¹ have been reported for unidentate coordinated nitrate⁵. The unidentate coordination of nitrate is further confirmed by overtone (2ν₁) and combination (ν₁+ν₄) bands⁴ of the nitrate in the region 1740–2030 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). Absorption bands in the range 1747–1785 cm⁻¹ have been observed due to ν₁+ν₄ combination and the value of ν₁ has been calculated from this by subtracting the value of ν₄. Another band in the range 1998–2028 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to overtone (2ν₁) and from this the value of ν₁ has been calculated. The ν₁

Table 1. Physical characteristics and analyses of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes^a

Compd.	Colour (Yield %)	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analyses (%) : Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			C	H	N ^a	M		
[CrL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (52)	185	39.71 (39.85)	5.90 (5.94)	10.28 (10.32)	9.46 (9.58)	3.96	107
[CrL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Green (62)	200	42.01 (42.10)	6.30 (6.35)	9.75 (9.82)	9.10 (9.11)	4.10	88
[FeL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (60)	205	39.54 (39.57)	5.89 (5.90)	10.28 (10.25)	10.36 (10.22)	6.41	95
[FeL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	Brown (61)	174	41.80 (41.82)	6.29 (6.31)	9.67 (9.75)	9.59 (9.72)	6.56	109
[CoL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]	Brown (94)	95	44.30 (44.35)	6.60 (6.61)	11.56 (11.49)	12.27 (12.09)	4.78	65
[CoL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]	Violet (63)	110	46.58 (46.60)	7.00 (7.03)	10.84 (10.86)	11.32 (11.43)	4.93	83

^aThe N values do not include nitrate nitrogen which is removed on treatment with H₂SO₄ in Kjeldahl's method.

values calculated from overtone and combination bands are almost same, which confirms the unidentate coordination of nitrate in the complexes.

Table 2. Overtone and combination bands (cm⁻¹) of unidentate coordinated nitrate ion

Compd.	v ₄	v ₁ +v ₄	v ₁	2v ₁	v ₁
	(obsvd.)	(obsvd.)	[(v ₁ +v ₄) - v ₄](obsvd.)	(2v ₁ /2)	(v ₁ /2)
[CrL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	748, 765	1757, 1771	1009, 1006	2015	1007
[CrL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	742, 760	1747, 1757	1005, 997	2000	1000
[FeL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	749, 777	1763, 1773	1014, 996	2008	1004
[FeL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]NO ₃	742, 786	1750, 1778	1008, 992	1998	999
[CoL ^I (NO ₃) ₂]	750, 771	1757, 1775	1007, 1004	2028	1014
[CoL ^{II} (NO ₃) ₂]	749, 774	1750, 1785	1001, 1011	2021	1010

Molar conductances : Molar conductances of the macrocyclic complexes are given in Table 1. For Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes molar conductances are in the range 88–109 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating 3 : 1 electrolytic behaviour⁶. Molar conductances of Co^{II} complexes are 65 and 83 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, which indicate their 2 : 1 electrolytic behaviour⁷. Thus it appears that the coordinated nitrate groups are replaced by the solvent molecules.

Magnetic moments : The magnetic moments of the complexes are given in Table 1. The μ_{eff} values for Cr^{III} com-

plexes are 3.96 and 4.10 B.M., which correspond to three unpaired electrons⁸. The μ_{eff} values for the Fe^{III} complexes are 6.41 and 6.56 B.M., which are consistent with high spin *d*⁵ system. These higher magnetic moments may be due to orbital contribution⁹. Gupta and Kushwah¹⁰ have reported magnetic moments upto 6.40 B.M. for Fe^{III} complexes of macrocycles derived from 4-methyl-2,6-di(formyl/benzoyl)-phenol and diamines. Cobalt(II) in its complexes seems to be in high spin state with magnetic moments 4.78 and 4.93 B.M. Higher values for Co^{II} may be due to orbital contribution. Chandra and Gupta¹¹ have reported μ_{eff} values in the range 4.99–5.05 B.M. for Co^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from acetylacetone and *o*- and *m*-phenylenediamine.

FAB mass spectra : The FAB mass spectra of Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} and Co^{II} complexes of macrocycles were recorded using NBA matrix and the spectrum of [Fe(Et₄[14]tetraeneN₄)(NO₃)₂]NO₃ is reproduced in Fig. 1. The peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289 and 307 are due to NBA matrix. All the spectra exhibit peaks due to molecular ions (M⁺) and free macrocycles (L⁺). This confirms the formation of macrocyclic complexes. In few complexes the peaks due to [M+H]⁺ have also been observed¹². In addition the spectra exhibit peaks assignable to various fragments arising from the

Fig. 1. FAB Mass spectrum of [Fe(Et₄[14]tetraeneN₄)(NO₃)₂]NO₃.

Scheme 2. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Fe}(\text{Et}_4[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$

thermal cleavage of the macrocycles and their complexes. The fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Fe}(\text{Et}_4[14]\text{tetraeneN}_4)(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3$ is given in Scheme 2. The complex shows a molecular ion peak at m/z 546 (2%) and $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ peak at 547 (46%). Fragment **b** is formed due to loss of nitrates from molecular ion **a** and appears at m/z 360 (35%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex.

(A) In this pathway the metal ion remains attached with the macrocyclic framework and step by step loss of four ethyl groups from **b** gives peaks at m/z 331 (19%), 302 (11%), 273 (6.8%) and 244 (8.2%) due to the species **c**, **d**, **e** and **f** respectively. Loss of iron atom from the species **f** finally gives the species **k**.

(B) In this pathway the metal ion may be lost from the macrocycle in the beginning and a peak at m/z 304 (6.8%) appears due to the free macrocycle **g**. Subsequent loss of four ethyl groups from the macrocycle gives peaks at m/z 275 (11%), 246 (7.6%), 217 (11%) and 188 (2%) due to the species **h**, **i**, **j** and **k** respectively¹³.

Electronic spectra : The diffuse reflectance spectra of Cr^{III} complexes exhibit four bands at 17094–17543, 20408–20833, 24096–24390 and 27027–27777 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (*a*), ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4B_{2g}$, ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ (*b*) and ${}^4B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}$ transitions respectively arising from the

lifting of the degeneracy of the orbital triplet (in octahedral symmetry) in the order of increasing energy and assuming effective D_{4h} symmetry around the metal ion¹¹. Spectra of Fe^{III} complexes exhibit strong charge transfer bands in the wavelength region below 500 nm, which obscures the observation of spin forbidden *d-d* transitions of very low intensity expected for the sextet state of Fe^{III} . However, a broad band at 10000 cm^{-1} is observed which may be due to spin forbidden transition ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (*a*)¹⁴. The lower energy bands ($\sim 17300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are probably due to splitting of ${}^4T_{1g}$ term and point towards the distorted nature of these complexes³. Co^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles show three bands in the region 7142–7558 (ν_1), 13072–13386 (ν_2) and 22123–23255 cm^{-1} (ν_3) which may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{1g}$ (*F*) $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (*F*) and ${}^4T_{1g}$ (*F*) $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (*P*) transitions respectively in an octahedral field¹⁵. The lower values of ν_2/ν_1 (1.7–1.8) may be due to distortion of the octahedral structure¹¹.

Experimental

1,3-Diaminopropane (Merck) and 1,4-diaminobutane (Merck) were distilled before use and 3,4-hexanedione (Merck) was used as supplied. $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all Fluka) were of A.R. grade.

Cr, Fe and Co were determined by standard methods¹⁶. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Carbon and hydrogen were determined by pregel combustion method on Hosti instrument that was standardized by benzoic acid. Magnetic measurements were carried out at room temperature (298 K) on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as a calibrant. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. The IR spectra (KBr) in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. The FAB Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 Kv, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded on Varian Cary 5E UV-VIS NIR spectrophotometer.

Synthesis of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes : Cr^{III}, Fe^{III} or Co^{II} nitrate (1.5 mmol) was dissolved in ~15 ml *n*-butanol and 3,4-hexanedione (3.0 mmol in ~10 ml *n*-butanol) was added with stirring. To this, a solution of 1,3-diaminopropane or 1,4-diaminobutane (3.0 mmol in ~10 ml *n*-butanol) was added dropwise with constant stirring, which was continued for 4–5 h. The solid appeared was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure (yields 52–94%).

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